

Introduction

Endometriosis

Enlargement of the tissues of the uterus or lining of the uterus is called endometriosis. This is very common disease known a days I young women's world wide. Tissues similar to endometrium is formed and change independently menstrual cycle.

Common systems;

- 1) Pain
- 2) Heavy bleeding /period lasts more than 7 days
- 3) Infertility
- 4) Constant fatigue
- 5) Ovarian cyst
- 6) Painful ovulation

stages of endometriosis

- minimal
- mild
- moderate
- severe

Endometriosis in Pakistan

One of the study conducted in 2017 concluded frequency of Endometriosis in women with infertility and sub-fertility was found to be 20%. They also found no association between demographic features age, Parity and socio-economic class and occurrence of endometriosis.

One more study is aimed in very next year 2018 to measure the level of DEHP in women's with endometriosis and without endometriosis the results shows that high level of DEHP which is a common EDCs women's exposed by the use of cosmetics and other products are also play the role of etiology of endometriosis and permit careful use of such compound .

Discussion or Next Steps

- Many different plants drug are used for the treatment of endometriosis. This review emphasis on the beneficial points on plants based drug such as *Allium sativum*, *Cupressus langsdorffii*, pines pin stir are checked out against endometriosis.
- There are many studies on endometriosis in Pakistan but no specific study shows the actual percentage of endometriosis in Pakistan. We need an extensive study to highlight this major disease in females.
- Therefore, we consider medicinal plants and phytochemicals excellent adjuncts in the treatment of endometriosis, but they are currently insufficient as unique therapeutic tools. The decision to consume such dietary supplements must be made with a doctor.

Methods

This review is based on the previous studies on endometriosis and cure to this diseases

Some of famous Plants and their effects against endometriosis

Viburnum opulus L.

Chlorogenic acid: Rats, surgically induced endometriosis used. Endometriotic volume decreases, Level of TNF- alpha, VEGF and IL-6 also decreases.

Allium sativum

When used in endometriotic cells it reduced cellular proliferation, induced apoptosis and Also show anti-angiogenic activity. Further show Decrease activity of VEGF and VEGFR expression.

Curcuma longa

Rat with surgically induced endometriosis decreased volume Of endometriotic lesions, anti-angiogenic effects, anti-inflammatory effects, pro-apoptotic and antioxidant activity also

References

1. Shaista Z, Hafsa S, Shereen ZB, SamiaShuja (2017) Prevalence of Endometriosis in Infertile and Sub-Fertile Women. SOJ Gynecol Obstet Womens Health 3(3)
2. Sadia N., Zeeshan U., Muneer I et al. (2018) womens diagnose with endometriosis show high llevel of diethyl hexyl phthalate. J Hum Reprod Sci. 11(2). 131-136.